

IIoT portable laser line profilometer powered by AI for gap and flush measurement in automotive

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Abstract—In automotive manufacturing, the final assembly of car body parts requires repeated measurements of gap and flush, which are essential not just for aesthetics but also for aerodynamics and noise reduction. This paper initially presents an innovative portable wireless laser line triangulation profilometer for human operators in assembly lines. It then describes how the wireless and ergonomic measurement device exploits embedded AI solutions to improve measurement accuracy. Two semantic segmentation approaches were tested (U-Net vs. LinkNet) to compare their performance in isolating the effective laser line from unwanted reflections, as well as inferring accurate segmentation with short inference times. These approaches were deployed at the edge, requiring pruning and quantization steps to comply with the computational capabilities of the System on Module (SoM) mounted on the device. The LinkNet demonstrated superior accuracy (Dice loss of 0.1127) and faster execution speed (166.77 ms). This approach, particularly with semantic segmentation algorithms implemented on the edge device, paves the way to improve the detection of laser line images on transparent surfaces even in the presence of low contrast and multiple reflections, ensuring precise and efficient measurement of gap and flush, even on front lights.

Keywords—Laser line triangulation, laser profilometer, Transparent surface, Artificial Intelligence, semantic segmentation, Automotive, Assembly line, Human-centric manufacturing, Zero defect manufacturing, Quality Control

I. INTRODUCTION

Since a decade, a convergence of concepts related to the fields of total quality, six-sigma policies, quality management and process/quality control have merged into the wider paradigm of Zero-Defect Manufacturing, which today is guiding the implementation of Industry 4.0 concepts in the manufacturing sector [1], [2], [3]. Even if many highly automated production systems exist, the involvement of operators in assembly and control operations in production lines is still, and will remain, a distinctive feature; in fact, human operators provide unparalleled autonomy and flexibility which in several situations, such as final assembly of vehicles car bodies, cannot be achieved by fully automated solutions. However, human operators are not directly connected to the digital factory environment, they perform

tasks, but almost no data are exchanged and stored in digital form; in practice today human operators have a very weak link to the digital factory. It is therefore increasingly important to digitally connect operators to the factory, so to integrate tasks performed by automated systems with those carried out by human operators, who will remain central to the manufacturing processes of the future. The so called Human-Centric Manufacturing (HCM) is a strategy that places the operator at the core of the production process, supported by smart tools and digital technologies [4]. Among the others, HCM emphasizes:

- Ergonomics and usability of tools;
- Skill enhancement and decision-making capabilities of the operator;
- Real-time data acquisition to support quality control.

Rather than removing the human element, HCM enhances it by providing operators with smart and portable devices, either tools or measurement systems, wireless and ergonomic, designed to empower human performance and to digitally connect them to the factory network. Focusing on tasks which require measurements, it is important to note that humans exhibit excellent flexibility and smartness, but also may lack of repeatability. Therefore, portable smart measurement devices should implement intelligent assistance, in order to keep measurement uncertainty under control.

This paper deals with these topics by addressing the final vehicle assembly, where precision and variability coexist. This combination necessitates manual operations and limits the extent to which automation can be applied.

Among the tasks performed by the operators during the final assembly of a car production line, there is the measurement of the gap and flush among parts of the cars, which are subject to specifications with tight tolerance.

- Gap: The space between two adjacent panels (e.g., door and fender);
- Flush: The height difference between the surfaces of two adjacent panels.

In the Body Shop area, where automation is extensive and product variability is minimal, these measurements are performed automatically, using non contact sensors mounted on robots and acquired data are fully available. However, in the Final Assembly area of the production line, the process

mainly relies on human operators, because it is required a large flexibility due to the large product variability, depending on the specific configuration of each car, and due to the many parts of different size, geometry, material to be assembled on the car body (doors, tail-gate, lights, aesthetic parts, bumpers, etc.).

Today, manual inspections of gap and flush are carried out at various stages of the vehicle final assembly. However, since these measurements are performed without electronic measurement devices, the measurement uncertainty heavily depends on the individual operator. Moreover, no data is generated or recorded from this inspection. These measurements rely on operators' tactile sense of alignment and on rough measurements made by feeler gauges and contact dials. Following these measurements, operators manually adjust components to the best of their capability. Currently, there is no information available regarding how many adjustments are made by operators during this process, which represents a critical gap. Moreover, no feedback is provided from the Final Assembly area back to the Body shop area.

The importance of gap and flush measurement and the difficulties and problems affecting such measurement are widely discussed in literature, see for example [5], [6], [7].

While several papers report on laser line triangulation sensors mounted on robots for automated measurement of gap and flush, not much literature exists on wireless portable devices designed for human operators. A non contact laser line triangulation integrated to a smart-phone was first presented in [8] as a result of a H2020 EU-funded project, named GOOD MAN [9]; the device was a demonstrator of the potential for empowerment of line operators in car assembly by providing them a small ergonomic hand-held devices. The question of measurement uncertainty of hand-held laser scanners for gap&flush measurement was then addressed in [10]. The innovative solution was patented [11]. Similarly, another smartphone based solution, again implementing the laser triangulation technique but using the camera of the smartphone, was presented in [12] and in [13].

However, solutions based on smartphones are not sufficiently robust for industrial use. Recently, within the Horizon Europe funded project openZDM [14], the G3F based on the cellular phone has been completely revised by the start-up U-Sense.IT, featuring a more industrial-oriented design and having all characteristics of an Industrial Internet of Things (IIoT).

In the market there are other portable laser profilometers, such as Gap Gun from Third Dimension, Calipri by Hexagon and Laser Gauge by LMI, however, the G3F is well differentiated from them, mainly in terms of dimensions, weight and ability to measure on different type of surfaces, like plastics, metal, etc.

In fact, one key feature of the new design presented in this paper is the ability to improve measurement accuracy by running application-specific, AI-based approaches directly on board, in particular semantic image segmentation algorithms to identify adjacent parts which have been patented [15]. This is made possible by the presence of a System on Module (SoM), which powers the device's computational capabilities with dedicated Neural Processing Units (NPU).

Particularly challenging for optical instruments is to measure gap and flush on transparent surfaces, such as lights, front lights, fully transparent, and rear lights, trans(a)parent and coloured, cause many reflections of the laser line, which often cause failure of conventional laser line extraction algorithms.

This paper, after presenting the hardware and software architecture of the IIoT device, shows how AI can improve laser line detection on transparent surfaces.

Overall, this paper discusses a measurement device designed to achieve zero-defect, fully aligned with the HCM approach that characterizes the Industry 5.0 framework.

The paper is organized as follows: Section II describes the portable laser line triangulation profilometer; Section III presents the AI-based solution developed to enhance the robustness of the measurements and expand its application range to transparent surfaces; Section IV provides experimental results demonstrating the potential of the proposed solution; and Section V summarizes the main conclusions of the work.

II. THE PORTABLE LASER LINE TRIANGULATION PROFILOMETER

A. The hardware architecture

The G3F device is a hand-held instrument based on laser line triangulation that measures the Gap and Flush values on different surfaces, i.e. metallic painted surfaces, rough metal surfaces, glass and plastic semi-transparent surfaces, etc. ... It mainly consists of:

- A. the optical part that is the core of the measurement instrument:
 - a. laser line projector;
 - b. camera;
 - c. lens.
- B. Electronic boards for managing the different HW peripherals and performing data processing on edge;
- C. Sensors like: a barcode reader, a Time of Flight Sensor, an IMU, a RGB sensor;
- D. a removable battery;
- E. the mechanical enclosure with the HMI.

An overview of the different components is reported in Fig. 1 (a) and (b).

The optical part has been designed in order to optimize the laser line projected with respect to the distance from the surfaces to be measured. The main components are the following:

- A laser source that operates in the violet region (405 nm) in Class 2M;
- A combination of lenses to convert a laser spot into a laser line having uniform intensity profile (spherical converging lens, diaphragm and Powell prism);
- A 5 Mpixel RGB camera to acquire the image of the laser line projected on the surface, equipped with a narrow band interference filter at the laser wavelength.

Fig. 1. The G3F device.

The geometry of the laser line triangulation is designed to allow a high spatial resolution over a small working range, taking into consideration typical values of gap and flush in automotive; the triangulation angle is set to 45° , the stand-off distance is set to allow operation from $z=0$ mm, i.e. in contact to the target surface, up to 12 mm distance, in non contact mode. Indeed, the device allows a hybrid contact or non-contact mode of operation.

The resulting characteristics of the G3F are presented in Table I.

TABLE I. G3F METROLOGIC CHARACTERISTICS

Working Range X (lateral)	17 mm (@ $Z=0$ mm)
	22 mm (@ $Z=12$ mm)
Working Range Z (axial)	0 ... 12 mm
Resolution X	7 μm (@ $Z=0$ mm)
	9 μm (@ $Z=12$ mm)
Resolution Z	9 μm

The G3F runs on a high-performance processing unit for a low-power System-on-Module, based on the i.MX 8M Plus family which is a set of NXP products focused on machine learning applications, combining state-of-art multimedia features with high-performance processing optimized for low-power consumption. Particularly, it embeds a Neural Processing Unit (NPU), suitable for image recognition. Indeed, the firmware specifically developed manages the measurement (profile acquisition by exploiting the embedded camera and the laser), the HMI (through the integrated display), and the processing of the acquired data.

Fig. 2.

Software architecture

As additional hardware, the device also embeds a time of flight (ToF) sensor to measure the device-to-target distance and an IMU (Inertial Measurement Unit). The device also embeds wireless connectivity to ensure the possibility to exchange the data acquired and receive job instructions from an external interface. Both WiFi and Bluetooth (BT 2.1+EDR and BLE 5.1) are available as wireless communication technologies. Remote connection to the system is guaranteed through SSH, while data exchange (e.g., images acquired, and profile extracted) is currently managed through the SFTP protocol. The device also hosts a local database that can be downloaded on remote platforms by the SFTP protocol.

B. The Software Architecture

An overview of the software architecture is illustrated in Fig. 2 and it is divided into two main parts:

- Peripheral Manager: the low-level SW to manage the hardware components of the device;
- G3F Manager: the high-level SW to manage the entire measurement process.

The Peripheral Manager SW has been developed in C; it is deployed on the Central Processing Unit (CPU) of the System on Module and it is responsible for the control and management of all the HW peripherals of the G3F, such as the camera, the barcode, the laser and the buttons' activation.

The G3F Manager SW has been developed in Python and it is deployed on the CPU of the SOM. It is responsible for the processing of the acquired image and the computation of the gap and flush values that are computed thanks to proprietary algorithms. Moreover, the AI algorithms are running on the Neural Processing Units (NPUs) integrated in the SOM. In the central part of Fig. 2, the different SW modules developed are reported, each of them responsible for a specific operation.

To extract the laser profile from the acquired image, the Center of Gravity (COG) algorithm has been used firstly, and then the gap and flush computation is performed as illustrated in Fig. 3, where on the left the raw image is shown and on the right side the mask representing the extracted profile from which the gap and flush quantities are computed is shown. It is important to note that the two adjacent surfaces are metal surfaces, therefore have good light scattering properties, which cause laser line to be clearly visible, without reflections and a good contrast.

Fig. 3. Laser line image (left) and extracted laser line profile (right). The two adjacent surfaces have good scattering properties, therefore laser line is clearly visible.

Fig. 4. G3F measuring on front lights

Fig. 5. Image of laser line on front lights: note that on the transparent part (left), corresponding to the lights, the laser line exhibits multiple reflections and a weak intensity.

For each measurement, the computed gap and flush values are compared with the threshold values provided and the results are shown to the operator through the G3F HMI and communicated through a MQTT protocol to the IT network. The data are then stored for further elaboration through the openZDM platform [14].

While the measurement of the gap and flush between metallic surfaces is accurate as the profile acquired is well defined, the measurement between different materials is still a challenge to be solved, in particular on the front lights surface of the car. When the sensor is positioned at the interface between a metallic part and the transparent surface (plastic or glass) of the head lamps, as illustrated in Fig. 4, the acquired image shows several problems which usually cause failure of state-of-art line search algorithms; in fact it is quite weak in intensity, and it consists of a number lines, caused by multiple reflections of the laser line, typically it appears a double reflection on the first and second surface of the transparent material and at least a third on the reflective mirror like surface of the bottom of the light. Sometimes the unwanted reflections have stronger intensity than the desired one, as shown in Fig.

5 (left part). In this condition, the classical line search algorithms, typically gradient filters, do not provide accurate and unique results and therefore different strategies have been studied and implemented in order to minimize the effect of the reflections.

An AI-based image cleansing approach has been developed to isolate the effective laser lines scattered by the first surface from the reflections developing on the rear surfaces of the lights. This model should make it possible to guarantee robust operations also on non-optically cooperative surfaces.

III. AI-BASED IMAGE CLEANSING

The presence of multiple reflections in the image, which is caused by light interactions with transparent (e.g., front/rear lights) and highly reflective surfaces (e.g., chromed parts), makes identifying the line profiles that correspond to the actual target surface a challenging task. Since the intensity levels of lines produced by these additional laser-surface interactions are comparable to or even weaker than those of the true target lines, traditional spatial filtering methods, thresholding techniques, and morphological operations often fail to yield satisfactory and robust results.

In contrast, AI-based solutions offer promising strategies to address these challenges, particularly due to their ability to generalize across varying working conditions (e.g., changes in ambient lighting, in target materials, etc.). Among the various AI-based approaches, semantic image segmentation is especially effective, as it enables the model to isolate target profiles from unwanted reflections; the target laser line profiles will be identified as a predicted region of the image, a mask. Once unwanted reflections are discarded, conventional laser line search algorithms will determine laser line profile.

However, while semantic segmentation is a well-established technique in computer vision, selecting the most effective strategies for embedded hardware remains a challenge, given its limited computational capacity. Neural Processing Units (NPUs) significantly aid in deploying efficient solutions, but further optimization is necessary to ensure acceptable performance in terms of segmentation accuracy and device responsiveness—i.e., the ability to produce results quickly enough to avoid disrupting the operator's workflow.

To address this, different model architectures were tested and optimized to run on the System on Module (SoM). The dataset used for training was created by collecting images from a real production line and labeling them using proprietary software.

A. U-Net

U-Net is a convolutional neural network (CNN) architecture designed for semantic image segmentation. It consists of an encoder and a decoder, forming the characteristic U shape [16]. The network has been adapted to run on the NPU coprocessor from NXP, which is integrated into the SoM of the G3F device. Specifically, the main modifications have been the following:

- replaced the Conv2DTranspose structures because they were not compatible with the delegate of the NXP VX delegate;

- applied integer quantization (uint8) of both the internal weights and tensors of input and output to be compatible with the new VX delegate;
- added Quantization Aware Training (QAT) to recover the loss of accuracy introduced by full integer quantization.

B. LinkNet

The LinkNet network is a convolutional neural network (CNN) architecture designed for efficient semantic segmentation, with a focus on speed and low memory consumption [17]. It consists of an encoder and a decoder with residual skip connections. The network has been adapted to run on NXP's NPU coprocessor, which powers the SOM, by applying the modifications already introduced in the U-Net.

C. The dataset

An initial available dataset of 2035 images was augmented by random operations of:

- RandomFlip("horizontal"),
- RandomRotation(0.05),
- RandomZoom(0.12),
- RandomTranslation(0.07, 0.07)

These were divided into train and test set in the percentage of 80% and 20% respectively. In this way, overall, 4884 train images and 407 test images were obtained.

The networks were trained with a custom loss function, which combines the Binary-Cross-entropy and the Dice loss, weighted according to an alpha parameter.

Training, testing, and exploring the hyperparameter space were all conducted on a workstation featuring two Intel®Xeon® Silver 4314 processors and three NVIDIA® A100 graphical processing units (GPU). The training phase took about 1 hour in the case of networks with the largest number of filters.

The final models were converted into TensorFlowLite representation, which is a lightweight version of TensorFlow designed specifically for deploying machine learning models on mobile, embedded, and edge devices. TensorflowLite makes use of platform-dependent delegates, a low-level implemented library, to execute the machine learning models using a specific hardware coprocessor to obtain native performance. In this work, we exploit the NXP VX delegate provided by the SOM platform to natively execute the proposed networks.

Neural Processing Units (NPUs) significantly aid in deploying efficient solutions, but further optimization is necessary to ensure acceptable performance in terms of segmentation accuracy and device responsiveness—i.e., the ability to produce results quickly enough to avoid disrupting the operator's workflow.

Relevant for the embedded systems is the battery consumption. In this case, there is no evidence in terms of an increased battery consumption due to the NPU use to run the AI model defined. The battery life is confirmed to be around 4 hours.

IV. RESULTS

Tables II and III report the performance and architecture characterization of the proposed LinkNet and U-Net, respectively, when varying the number of convolutional filters in the first layer. In particular, the segmentation accuracy is reported in terms of Dice Loss, while the NN efficiency is reported in inference and warmup times measured on top of the G3F device.

TABLE II. PERFORMANCE AND ARCHITECTURE CHARACTERIZATION OF THE LINKNET NETWORK

LinkNet				
Filters #	Model size [KB]	Dice Loss	Warmup time [ms]	Inference time [ms]
16	763	0.1407	6592	131.86
32	2900	0.1154	9051	146.91
64	11366	0.1127	21376	166.77

TABLE III. PERFORMANCE AND ARCHITECTURE CHARACTERIZATION OF THE U-NET NETWORK

U-Net				
Filters #	Model size [KB]	Dice Loss	Warmup time [ms]	inference time [ms]
16	714	0.1724	3444	227.49
32	2535	0.1244	5789	344.78
64	10445	0.1222	12334	876.43

The most effective network was LinkNet, which demonstrated superior accuracy (Dice loss of 0.1127) and faster execution speed (166.77 ms). The lower performance of the U-Net network is primarily due to the high loss of accuracy it incurred in the full-integer quantization phase, which was only partly recovered by the QAT technique. Furthermore, the U-Net network demonstrated significantly higher inference times, with a processing speed up to seven times slower than LinkNet. Conversely, concerning the warmup time, it is interesting to note that U-Net results in the fastest network. This time is primarily attributed to model deserialization, interpreter instantiation, memory allocation, and the initialization of computational delegates for the SoM NPU. To mitigate this effect, it is sufficient to explicitly create the interpreter and perform a preliminary inference with placeholder data at device startup, thereby amortizing the warm-up cost before starting operation.

Fig.6 shows the accuracy and loss values measured during the training phase of the LinkNet with 32 convolutional filters, both for training and validation data. The network rapidly attains optimal performance (at approximately epoch 25), indicating effective training stability.

Fig.6. Accuracy and loss values measured during the training phase of the LinkNet with 32 convolutional filters.

Fig 7. Several examples of predicted output together with the input image and the expected results.

As a final result, Fig 7 shows four examples of the network output (PREDICTED MASK), starting from the input image (INPUT) and compared with the ground truth (MASK), together with the value of the Dice Loss calculated between the mask and the prediction. Qualitatively, the predicted masks appear to accurately reflect the expected results, even when the Dice Loss value is still significant. For instance, in the third row, its value reaches 0.20, but it seems clear that the high value is due to the predicted mask having a longer length on the left end than on the ground truth, and not from incorrect segmentation or misalignment. Also, in the other cases, for Dice Loss values around 0.15 and above, no appreciable prediction problems correspond or can compromise the usability of the model. Moreover, in several cases, the not-so-low loss values can be attributed to differences in the mask stroke, sometimes more flickering or less sharp in the expected mask than predicted, or to smearing at the start and end points.

V. CONCLUDING REMARKS

The paper presented an innovative IIoT portable laser line triangulation profilometer, wireless and ergonomic,

designed for human operators in assembly lines; the device constitutes by itself a significant advancement in non-contact surface metrology with respect to state-of-art. It has been engineered and now it is market ready. The use of the device in the automotive quality control performed in the Final Assembly will provide a reduction of 50% of the time needed by the operator to perform the gap and flush controls, because both measurements are performed simultaneously.

Main features of the device are its miniature size and ergonomic, as well as a measurement range designed to allow a hybrid contact or non-contact mode of operation for gap and flush measurement on cars. The integration of laser technology, precision optics, a camera, several sensors over a digital architecture based on a SOM, makes the system at all extents an edge device which allows the inline operators to perform measurements and connects them to the factory network, as required for a human-centric approach to manufacturing.

The device is powered by AI algorithms, implementing semantic segmentation, thus realizing a system that overcomes the limitations of conventional measurement techniques while offering exceptional versatility across diverse material surfaces and industrial environments. It has been shown how this approach performs in the challenging case of transparent surfaces, such as front lights; the laser line image in this case has multiple unwanted and unavoidable reflections and low contrast, therefore conventional algorithms fail. Instead, the semantic segmentation running on the edge device allows to correctly identify the laser line to be processed, define a mask around it and discard the lines caused by unavoidable reflections.

It has been shown how these AI algorithms implemented on board run efficiently on the edge device and allow in-line measurements on difficult surfaces such as front lights to be completed within the typical time available. It is expected that this approach will guarantee performance for a wide range of applications, where the influence of surface materials creates poor quality images of the laser line.

ACKNOWLEDGMENT

This work was partially supported by the European Project openZDM (Grant Agreement No. 101058673, call HORIZON-CL4-2021-TWINTRANSITION-01) for the part related to the sensor development and by the “PR MARCHE FESR 2021/2027 – ASSE 1 – OS 1.1– AZIONE 1.1.6 – Intervento 1.1.6.1 – SOSTEGNO ALL’AVVIO E AL CONSOLIDAMENTO DELLE START UP INNOVATIVE” for the part related to the AI implementation on edge.

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